

acephate treatments. The differences in results from the cited paddy-water study and from the contact toxicity study reported here may be due to different modes of action of the insecticide in the two application methods. Insecticides applied in the paddy water may have acted primarily as a stomach poison, but the insecticides in this study acted as contact poisons, entering through the cuticle rather than the mouthparts. At any rate, knowing that BPH biotypes differ in their susceptibility to insecticides is important and should be considered when developing strategies for BPH control. **W**

Contact toxicity of insecticides applied with Potter's spray tower at 0.04% concentration against three brown planthopper biotypes. IIRI greenhouse, 1977.

Insecticide	Formulation	Mortality ^a (%)		
		Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
Decamethrin	2.5 EC	93 a	97 a	90 a
Carbofuran	2 F	68 b	98 a	97 a
Metalkamate	30 EC	64 b	99 a	97 a
Acephate	75 SP	37 a	47 a	37 a
Diazinon	20 EC	24 b	49 a	43 a
Methyl parathion	50 EC	11 b	47 a	35 a
Control		6 a	6 a	4 a

^aMortality reading taken 48 hours after treatment. Average of 4 replications, each consisting of 25 adult insects. Any means for each biotype followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Resistance of brown planthopper to various insecticides at IIRI

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In 1977 carbofuran failed to control the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* at IIRI. Studies using Potter's spray tower and paddy water broadcast methods of application indicated that the strain of BPH that had been exposed to carbofuran for several years (field strain) was resistant (see article, this issue). Further studies using the microapplicator were conducted to compare the field strain's level of resistance to carbofuran and to other insecticides with that of a greenhouse strain that had not been exposed to insecticides.

Both sexes of the field strain had seven times more resistance to carbofuran than the greenhouse strain (see table). The field strain had two to five times

The LD₅₀ value of insecticides applied topically to greenhouse and field strains^a of female and male brown planthoppers. IIRI laboratory, 1977.

Insecticide	Female		ERR ^b	Male		ERR ^b
	LD ₅₀ (µg/g)			LD ₅₀ (dg)		
	Greenhouse strain	Field strain		Greenhouse strain	Field strain	
Carbofuran	0.14	1.05	7.50	0.25	1.78	7.12
Monocrotophos	0.65	3.50	5.38	0.49	2.00	4.08
Metalkamate	1.46	5.37	3.67	2.00	8.68	4.34
Methyl parathion	7.67	23.19	3.02	10.52	13.90	1.32
BPMC	1.95	5.29	2.71	2.89	11.80	4.08
MIPC	1.42	3.29	2.30	5.23	5.59	1.06
Endosulfan	3.09	5.94	1.92	5.12	12.46	2.43
Acephate	2.93	4.96	1.69	3.56	7.79	2.18
N 3727	28.90	32.43	1.12	41.46	43.41	1.04
Perthane	5.13	5.70	1.11	4.45	10.46	2.35
A47171	4.07	4.07	1.00	6.66	5.81	0.87

^aThe greenhouse strain had not been exposed to insecticide and was reared in the greenhouse for about 30 generations. The field strain was reared in the greenhouse for about 4 generations.

^bEstimated resistance ratio = LD₅₀ of field strain divided by LD₅₀ of greenhouse strain.

more resistance to other insecticides that had been used to varying extents at the IIRI farm. Monocrotophos and MIPC have been most commonly used for about

5 years. There was no resistance to newly developed coded compounds, such as N 3727 and A 47171, that had never been used on the farm. **W**

Heavy brown planthopper reinfestations nullify effectiveness of insecticides

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Insecticidal control has often been insufficiently effective against the brown planthopper (BPH) during massive outbreaks over extensive areas. Rapid

and heavy reinfestations from unaffected BPH populations probably are a significant reason, particularly where the entire affected area cannot be treated effectively, uniformly, and simultaneously, as is common under normal field conditions. This was especially evident in recent insecticide trials in Sekinchan, Malaysia, during a BPH outbreak on the rice variety MR 7 at 20 to 26 days after transplanting.

Two fields of 2 ha each were treated with 2 kg a.i. carbofuran/ha (granular broadcast) and 0.1% a.i. monocrotophos (foliar), respectively. Immediately after treatment, 10 plants spaced over each field were randomly selected; each plant was individually enclosed with cylindrical wire and nylon screen cages. The BPH populations on these plants were determined just before treatment and periodically afterwards. Similar BPH